

Questioning the Growth Dogma: A Replication Study

Online Appendix

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In this appendix, we present the procedures used for this paper:

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In particular, we present the different steps in the treatment and analysis of the data and the syntax, either SAS or STATA, used.

Following recommendations for high-quality replications, we conducted our replication systematically and moved in stages. First, we replicated the original study on different samples but otherwise relied on similar measures and methods. This is to assess whether the results are affected by the characteristics of the sample or whether they generalize to new populations. Second, we performed several alternative estimation methods to assess the robustness of the original study's results. The first stage however was to constitute our sample and operationalize the variables.

Step 1: Importation of data

Amadeus does not allow importing all the large datasets at once. Thus, we had first to import all the 107 datasets. To facilitate the importation procedure we named all the datasets E with a number ranging from 1 to 107 and they were all stored in the same file. We then piled up the 107 datasets to create our data set.

SAS Syntax for Step 1

```
proc      import      datafile      =      'C:\Users\anais.hamelin\Seafile\Anaïs\Publi\EN  
Revision\Cyrine_replication\ETP_V2\BASES_NEW\E_1.xlsx'  
DBMS = xlsx OUT = E1;  
run;  
  
data E; set E1-E107;  
run;
```

Step 2: Formatting the data

The variables imported from Amadeus are not all well formatted and we had some issues with some variables that are considered as characters, and not numerical variables, because Amadeus codes “n.d” text for missing variables.

Moreover some variable names are lost during the importation due to the fact that they are too long, thus we need to rename the variables. Finally, some variables needed to be recoded, such as industries from the initial NACE codes (EU equivalent of SIC codes).

SAS Syntax for Step 2

```
/**Renaming variables ***/
```

```
data E; set E;  
New_VAR=Initial_VAR_Name;  
run;
```

```
/**Recoding missing values in SAS language (replacing “n.d” by “.” and transforming numerical variables that are imported as character variables***/
```

```
data E; set E;  
if New_VAR =“n.d” then New_VAR =.;  
New_VAR2= input (New_VAR, best12.);  
run;
```

```
/** Creating a unique identifier by firms, which are identified in the initial data by Num_ro_BvD, which is heavy to manipulate***/
```

```
data id; set E;  
keep Num_ro_BvD;  
run;
```

```
proc sort data=id nodupkey;  
by Num_ro_BvD;  
run;
```

```
data id; set id;  
retain id 0;  
id=id+1;run;
```

```
proc sort data=E;  
by Num_ro_BvD;  
run;
```

```
data E;  
merge id E;  
by Num_ro_BvD;
```

```

run;

/** Creating a unique identifier by firms-year observations (cpt)***/

data E; set E;
retain cpt 0;
cpt=cpt+1;
run;

```

Step 3: Transforming data into a panel

Initial Amadeus data contains one variable per year. Thus, if we have 8 years of observation we have 8 variables for sales for example. In order to transform the initial data set into a panel we use the following macro.

```

SAS Syntax for Step 3

/** Rename all the time varying variable***/

data E; set E;
VAR_year=Varyear;
run;

%Macro annee;
%do i=2011 %to 2019;
data E&i.; set E;
year=&i.;
VAR=VAR_&i.;
keep id VAR non_time_varying_variables;
%end;
%mend;
%annee;
run;

data E; set E2011-E2019;
run;

```

Step 4: Building time-invariant variables at the firm level

As is often the case, we needed to code new variables from the information extracted from the database.

```

SAS Syntax for Step 4

```

```
/** Creating a table at the firm level, with time-invariant variables, based on the first year in which the firm enters the database ***/
```

```
proc sort data=E ;  
by Num_ro_BvD year;  
run;
```

```
Data E_T; set E;  
run;
```

```
proc sort data=E_T nodupkey;  
by Num_ro_BvD;  
run;
```

```
/** We exclude from the sample, firms for which we did not have any info on characteristics used in the study: size, BG affiliation status, industry ***/
```

```
Data E_T; set E_T;  
if NEMP =. then delete;  
if nbent_groupe =. then delete;  
if secteur="A" then delete;  
if secteur="O" then delete;  
if secteur="T" then delete;  
run;
```

```
/** We exclude from the sample firms that were not SMEs when entering the sample and for which we did not have or incoherent information on the number of employees***/
```

```
Data E_T; set E_T;  
if NEMP > 250 then delete;  
if NEMP <0 then delete;  
if totasset < 0 then delete;  
run;
```

```
/** Code for class size, business groups size, and industry classification, and exclusion of missing information***/
```

```
Data E_T; set E_T;  
if NEMP<50 and NEMP>=10 then taille=1;  
if NEMP>=50 then taille=2;  
if NEMP<10 then taille=0;  
if nbent_groupe <6 then taille_G=0;  
if nbent_groupe >6 then taille_G=1;  
if nbent_groupe <2 then groupe =0;  
if nbent_groupe>=2 then groupe =1;  
if groupe=0 then taille_G=.;  
if secteur="B" then industry =1;
```

```

if secteur="C" then industry =1;
if secteur="D" then industry =1;
if secteur="E" then industry =1;
if secteur="F" then industry =1;
if secteur="G" then industry =2;
if secteur="H" then industry =2;
if secteur="I" then industry =3;
if secteur="J" then industry =3;
if secteur="K" then industry =3;
if secteur="L" then industry =3;
if secteur="M" then industry =3;
if secteur="N" then industry =3;
if secteur="P" then industry =4;
if secteur="Q" then industry =4;
if secteur="R" then industry =4;
if secteur="S" then industry =4;
ok=1;
keep Num_ro_BvD ok industry taille taille_G groupe ;
run;

/**** Merging with the panel database****/

proc sort data=E_T;
by Num_ro_BvD;
run;

data E;
merge E E_T;
by Num_ro_BvD;
if ok ne 1 then delete;
run;

```

Step 5: Computation of panel variables

Then we build the panel variables and use the lag function to build the growth variables.

SAS Syntax for Step 5

```

/**** Computing performance ratios****/

data E; set E;
ROA=RN/Totasset;
ROCE=REx/totasset;
ROE=RN/CP;
levier=DLT/CP;

```

```

run;

/**** Computing growth rates, using lag values****/

proc sort data=E;
by Num_ro_BvD year;
run;

%macro Lag;
%do j=1 %to 9;
proc expand data=E out=E method=none;
id cpt;
convert var=var&j./transform=(lag &j.);
convert id=id&j./transform=(lag &j.);
%end;
%mend;
%Lag;
run;

data E; set E;
%macro ident;
%do i=1 %to 9;
varCA&i.=(CA-CA&i.)/ca&i.;
if id ne id&i. then varCA&i.=.;
vartotasset&i.=(totasset-totasset&i.)/totasset&i.;
if id ne id&i. then totasset&i.=.;
varNEMP&i.=(NEMP-NEMP&i.)/NEMP&i.;
if id ne id&i. then NEMP&i.=.;
%end;
%mend;
%ident;
run;

/**** Excluding from the sample observations for which we do not have a growth rates or a
performance measure****/

data E; set E;
if VARCA1=. then delete;
if ROA=. then delete;
run;

```

Step 6: Building the different samples

In our study, we use different samples: the full sample, but also two stratified samples. In order to build stratified samples we used two alternative methodologies. The first one consists in defining strata according to different variables (in our case as we followed the original study, we defined strata according to firm size, business group affiliation, industry). The second one consists in a stratification of the sample across countries and class size to mimic the EU SMEs population.

SAS Syntax for Step 6

```
/** Building a stratified sample following Davidsson et al. (2009)**/
```

```
data E_S1; set E;  
run;
```

```
proc sort data= E_S1;  
by id year;  
run;
```

```
proc sort data=E_S1 nodupkey;  
by id;  
run;
```

```
data E_S1; set E_S1;  
if taille=1 and taille_G=0 and industry=1 then strate=1;  
if taille=1 and taille_G=0 and industry=2 then strate=2;  
if taille=1 and taille_G=0 and industry=3 then strate=3;  
if taille=1 and taille_G=0 and industry=4 then strate=4;  
if taille=1 and taille_G=1 and industry=1 then strate=5;  
if taille=1 and taille_G=1 and industry=2 then strate=6;  
if taille=1 and taille_G=1 and industry=3 then strate=7;  
if taille=1 and taille_G=1 and industry=4 then strate=8;  
if taille=2 and taille_G=1 and industry=1 then strate=9;  
if taille=2 and taille_G=1 and industry=2 then strate=10;  
if taille=2 and taille_G=1 and industry=3 then strate=11;  
if taille=2 and taille_G=1 and industry=4 then strate=12;  
if taille=2 and taille_G=0 and industry=1 then strate=13;  
if taille=2 and taille_G=0 and industry=2 then strate=14;  
if taille=2 and taille_G=0 and industry=3 then strate=15;  
if taille=2 and taille_G=0 and industry=4 then strate=16;  
if taille=1 and taille_G=. and industry=1 then strate=17;  
if taille=1 and taille_G=. and industry=2 then strate=18;  
if taille=1 and taille_G=. and industry=3 then strate=19;  
if taille=1 and taille_G=. and industry=4 then strate=20;  
if taille=2 and taille_G=. and industry=1 then strate=21;  
if taille=2 and taille_G=. and industry=2 then strate=22;  
if taille=2 and taille_G=. and industry=3 then strate=23;  
if taille=2 and taille_G=. and industry=4 then strate=24;
```

```

run;

proc sort data= E_S1;
by strate;
run;

PROC SURVEYSELECT
  DATA = E_S1
  OUT = E_S1_1
  SAMPSIZE = 110 SELECTALL;
  STRATA strate ;
RUN ;

data E_S1_1; set E_S1_1;
sample=1;
keep id strate sample;
run;

proc sort data= E_S1_1;
by id;
run;

data E_S1_1; merge E E_S1_1;
by id;
run;

data E_S1_1; set E_S1_1;
if sample ne 1 then delete;
if cpt=. then delete;
run;

/****Building the Eurostat stratified sample****/

/**** Creating sub sample by countries and firm size****/

data echant; set E;
if Pays="GR" then delete
if Pays = "CY" then delete;
run;

proc sort data=echant;
by id year;
run;

proc sort data=echant nodupkey;
by id;

```

run;

proc means data=echant;

run;

data testa; set echant;

if taille<=1 and pays="AT" then strate=1;
if taille<=1 and pays="BE" then strate=2;
if taille<=1 and pays="BG" then strate=3;
if taille<=1 and pays="CZ" then strate=4;
if taille<=1 and pays="DE" then strate=5;
if taille<=1 and pays="DK" then strate=6;
if taille<=1 and pays="EE" then strate=7;
if taille<=1 and pays="ES" then strate=8;
if taille<=1 and pays="FI" then strate=9;
if taille<=1 and pays="FR" then strate=10;
if taille<=1 and pays="HR" then strate=11;
if taille<=1 and pays="HU" then strate=12;
if taille<=1 and pays="IE" then strate=13;
if taille<=1 and pays="IT" then strate=14;
if taille<=1 and pays="LT" then strate=15;
if taille<=1 and pays="LU" then strate=16;
if taille<=1 and pays="LV" then strate=17;
if taille<=1 and pays="MT" then strate=18;
if taille<=1 and pays="NL" then strate=19;
if taille<=1 and pays="PL" then strate=20;
if taille<=1 and pays="PT" then strate=21;
if taille<=1 and pays="RO" then strate=22;
if taille<=1 and pays="SE" then strate=23;
if taille<=1 and pays="SI" then strate=24;
if taille<=1 and pays="SK" then strate=25;
if taille<=1 and pays="GB" then strate=26;
if taille=2 and pays="AT" then strate=27;
if taille=2 and pays="BE" then strate=28;
if taille=2 and pays="BG" then strate=29;
if taille=2 and pays="CZ" then strate=30;
if taille=2 and pays="DE" then strate=31;
if taille=2 and pays="DK" then strate=32;
if taille=2 and pays="EE" then strate=33;
if taille=2 and pays="ES" then strate=34;
if taille=2 and pays="FI" then strate=35;
if taille=2 and pays="FR" then strate=36;
if taille=2 and pays="HR" then strate=37;
if taille=2 and pays="HU" then strate=38;
if taille=2 and pays="IE" then strate=39;
if taille=2 and pays="IT" then strate=40;

```

if taille=2 and pays="LT" then strate=41;
if taille=2 and pays="LU" then strate=42;
if taille=2 and pays="LV" then strate=43;
if taille=2 and pays="MT" then strate=44;
if taille=2 and pays="NL" then strate=45;
if taille=2 and pays="PL" then strate=46;
if taille=2 and pays="PT" then strate=47;
if taille=2 and pays="RO" then strate=48;
if taille=2 and pays="SE" then strate=49;
if taille=2 and pays="SI" then strate=50;
if taille=2 and pays="SK" then strate=51;
if taille=2 and pays="GB" then strate=52;
run;

```

```

proc sort data=testa;
by strate;
run;

```

```

proc means data=testa;
run;

```

```

proc freq data=testa;
table strate;
run;

```

```

data testi; set testa;
if pays="LU" then delete;
if pays="MT" then delete;
run;

```

```

%macro tesa;
%do i=1 %to 52;
data tes&i.; set testi;
if strate ne &i. then delete;
%end;
%mend;
%tesa;
run;

```

/** Picking a random sample for each strata: for each strata changing the number 1 by the strata number (1 to 52) and N= by the number of observations for each strata, where the numbers in N are defined as to maximize the sample size while maintaining the stratification**

```

PROC SURVEYSELECT
DATA = tes1
OUT = t1
Method = SRS N="N" ;

```

```

/** Merging the samples***/
DATA ue1; set t1-t15;
run;
data ue2; set t19-t41;
run;
data ue3; set t45-t52;
run;
data strat_UE; set ue1 ue2 ue3 t17 T43;
run;

data strat; set strat_UE;
UE_sample=1;
keep id UE_sample;
run;

proc sort data=strat nodupkey;
by id;
run;

Data E; merge strat E;
by id;
if UE_sample ne 1 then delete;
run;

```

Notice: In what follows we present the process for the full sample (data=E) but the same steps need to be repeated for each sample, just changing the name of the data set for specific subsamples.

Step 7: Computing sample specific variables

In our research, we needed to compute several variables that are specific to the sample as they are adjusted or compared to the other observations.

SAS Syntax for Step 7

```

/** Computation of performance indicators adjusted by industry and year median***/

proc sort data=E;
by secteur year;
run;

```

```

proc univariate data=E noprint;
by secteur year;
var varCA1 ROA;
output out = meant2 median=varCA1medianS  median=ROAmedianS;
run;

data E ;
merge E meant2;
by secteur year;
ROA_ADJ=ROA/ROAmedianS;
VARCA_ADJ=varCA1/varCA1medianS;
s=1;
run;

/****Creation of categorical variable of performance following Davidsson et al. (2009)****/

Proc univariate data= E noprint;
var ROA_ADJ VARCA_ADJ;
output out = meant median=varCA_ADJ  median=ROA_ADJ ;
run;

data meant1; set meant;
MED_ROA=ROA_ADJ;
MED_VARCA=varCA_ADJ;
s=1;
keep s MED_ROA MED_VARCA;
run;

Proc univariate data= E noprint;
var ROA_ADJ VARCA_ADJ;
output out = meant Q3=varCA_ADJ Q3=ROA_ADJ;
run;

data m1; set meant;
Q3_ROA=ROA_ADJ;
Q3_VARCA=varCA_ADJ;
s=1;
keep s Q3_ROA Q3_VARCA;
run;

Proc univariate data= E noprint;
var ROA_ADJ VARCA_ADJ;
output out = meant Q1=varCA_ADJ Q1=ROA_ADJ;
run;

data ma1; set meant;

```

```

Q1_ROA=ROA_ADJ;
Q1_VARCA=varCA_ADJ;
s=1;
keep s Q1_ROA Q1_VARCA;
run;

data mit1; merge ma1 m1 meant1;
by s;
run;

data E; merge mit1 E;
by s;
run;

data E; set E;
if ROA_ADJ >Q1_ROA and ROA_ADJ<=Q3_ROA and VARCA_ADJ<= Q3_VARCA and
VARCA_ADJ>Q1_VARCA then Middle=1; else Middle=0;
if ROA_ADJ > MED_ROA and VARCA_ADJ<= MED_VARCA and middle=0 then profit=1;
else profit=0;
if ROA_ADJ <=MED_ROA and VARCA_ADJ>MED_VARCA and middle=0 then growth=1;
else growth=0;
if ROA_ADJ >Q3_ROA and VARCA_ADJ> MED_VARCA and middle=0 then star=1;
if ROA_ADJ >MED_ROA and VARCA_ADJ> Q3_VARCA and middle=0 then star=1;
if star ne 1 then star = 0;
if ROA_ADJ <=Q1_ROA and VARCA_ADJ<= MED_VARCA and middle=0 then poor=1;
if ROA_ADJ <=MED_ROA and VARCA_ADJ< Q1_VARCA and middle=0 then poor=1;
if poor ne 1 then poor = 0;
run;

```

Step 8: Computation of transitions

We developed a macro in order to create the variables of transition: in order to identify in which class the firm is after one and up to eight years.

SAS Syntax for Step 8

```

proc sort data=E;
by id descending year;
run;

data test; set E ;
retain cpt_bis 0;
cpt_bis=cpt_bis+1;
run;

```

```

data tot; set test;
keep id year;
run;
/**/ identification of exiting firms before the end, 2019, of the sample***/

proc sort data=tot ;
by id descending year;
run;

proc sort data=tot nodupkey;
by id ;
run;

data tot; set tot;
if year=2019 then delete;
run;

data tot; set tot;
exit=1;
run;

/**/ Creation of new class variables for each length of transition***/

data t; merge tot test;
by id descending year;
run;

%macro Lag;
%do j=1 %to 8;
proc expand data=t out=t method=none;
id cpt_bis;
convert poor=poor&j./transform=(lag &j.);
convert star=star&j./transform=(lag &j.);
convert growth=growth&j./transform=(lag &j.);
convert profit=profit&j./transform=(lag &j.);
convert middle=middle&j./transform=(lag &j.);
convert exit=exit&j./transform=(lag &j.);
convert id=id&j./transform=(lag &j.);
%end;
%mend;
%Lag;
run;

%macro propre;
data t; set t;
%do i=1 %to 8;
if id ne id&i. then poor&i.=.;

```

```

if id ne id&i. then star&i.=.;
if id ne id&i. then middle&i.=.;
if id ne id&i. then profit&i.=.;
if id ne id&i. then growth&i.=.;
if id ne id&i. then exit&i.=.;
%end;
%mend;
%propre;
run;

```

```

data test; set t;
if exit8=1 then exit9=1;
if exit7=1 then exit8=1;
if exit6=1 then exit7=1;
if exit5=1 then exit6=1;
if exit4=1 then exit5=1;
if exit3=1 then exit4=1;
if exit2=1 then exit3=1;
if exit1=1 then exit2=1;
if exit=1 then exit1=1;
run;

```

```

data test; set test;
if exit1=1 then exit=0;
if exit2=1 then exit1=0;
if exit3=1 then exit2=0;
if exit4=1 then exit3=0;
if exit5=1 then exit4=0;
if exit6=1 then exit5=0;
if exit7=1 then exit6=0;
if exit8=1 then exit7=0;
if exit9=1 then exit8=0;
RUN;

```

```

%macro propre2;
data test; set test;
%do i=1 %to 8;
if exit&i.=1 then poor&i.=0;
if exit&i.=1 then star&i.=0;
if exit&i.=1 then middle&i.=0;
if exit&i.=1 then profit&i.=0;
if exit&i.=1 then growth&i.=0;
%end;
%mend;
%propre2;
run;

```

```
data E; set test; run;
```

Step 9: Descriptive statistics

SAS Syntax for Step 9

```
/** Sample descriptive statistics (Table B)***/  
  
proc means data=E;  
var ROA varCA1 Totasset age groupe;  
run;  
  
/** 1-year transitions percentages (Table C) ***/  
Data E; set E;  
if poor=1 then synth="Poor";  
if Middle=1 then synth="Middle";  
if growth=1 then synth="Growth";  
if profit=1 then synth="Profit";  
if star=1 then synth="Star";  
if poor1=1 then synth1="Poor";  
if Middle1=1 then synth1="Middle";  
if growth1=1 then synth1="Growth";  
if profit1=1 then synth1="Profit";  
if star1=1 then synth1="Star";  
if exit1=1 then synth1="Exit";  
run;  
  
proc freq data=E;  
table synth*synth1 ;  
run;  
  
/** Number of transition observed (Table D) *****/  
  
data E; set E;  
if growth=1 then synth="Growth";  
if profit=1 then synth="Profit";  
run;  
  
proc freq data=E;  
table synth*star1  
synth*POOR1  
synth*star2  
synth*star3  
synth*star4
```

```
synth*star5  
synth*star6  
synth*star7  
synth*star8 ; run;
```

Step 10: Comparison of transitions to Star/Poor categories between Growth and Star Firms

The same program is used to produce tables 1 to 5 in the paper. We only change the sample or the variables of performance.

SAS Syntax for Step 10

```
/** Transitions to Star***/  
  
%macro freq;  
%do i=1 %to 8;  
proc freq data=E;  
table star&i.*growth/ out=G&i.;  
table star&i.*profit/ out=P&i.;  
data G&i.; set G&i.;  
if growth ne 1 then delete;  
data P&i.; set P&i.;  
if profit ne 1 then delete;  
data F&i.; set G&i. P&i.;  
if growth=1 then treatment="growth";  
if profit=1 then treatment="profit";  
if star&i=. then delete;  
proc freq data=F&i.;  
weight count;  
tables treatment*star&i./relrisk riskdiff;  
%end;  
%mend;  
%freq;  
run;  
  
/** Transitions to Poor***/  
  
%macro freq;  
%do i=1 %to 8;  
proc freq data=E;  
table poor&i.*growth/ out=G&i.;  
table poor&i.*profit/ out=P&i.;  
data G&i.; set G&i.;  
if growth ne 1 then delete;  
data P&i.; set P&i.;  
if profit ne 1 then delete;
```

```

data F&i.; set G&i. P&i.;
if growth=1 then treatment="growth";
if profit=1 then treatment="profit";
if poor&i.=. then delete;
proc freq data=F&i.;
weight count;
tables treatment*poor&i./relrisk riskdiff;
%end;
%mend;
%freq;
run;

```

Step 11: Probit estimation of the likelihood to transition to Star/Poor (Table 6)

For the probit analysis, we use the software STATA, by exporting our SAS table into STATA format, through the export feature of SAS. The same program is used for computing the transitions to Star or Poor. We only change the explained variable (from Star to Poor) in the model statement.

STATA Syntax for Step 11

```

/**** Restriction of the sample to growth or profit firms****/
keep if growth==1 |profit==1

/**** Declaring the data as panel variable, id identify each firms****/
xtset id year, yearly

/****Construction of variables****/
generate size = log(TOTasset)

/**** Declaring the data as panel variable, id identify each firms****/
xtset id year, yearly

/**** Specification 1****/
xtprobit star1 profit

/**** Specification 2****/
xtprobit star1 profit size age i.pays i.year i.industry

/**** Specification 3****/
xtprobit star1 profit growth size age i.pays i.year i.industry,re

/**** Specification 4****/
xtprobit star2 profit1 growth1 profit growth size age i.pays i.year i.industry,re

/**** Specification 5****/

```

```
xtprobit star3 profit2 growth2 profit1 growth1 profit growth size age i.pays i.year i.industry,re
```

Step 12: Nearest neighbor match sample treatment effect (Table 7)

In order to perform this analysis we rely on the `teffects nnmatch` procedure of STATA.

STATA Syntax for Step 12

```
/***/ Restriction of the sample to growth or profit firms****/  
keep if growth==1 |profit==1
```

```
/***/ Code for the 1- year up to 7-year transition ****/  
teffects nnmatch (Star1 size age year industry pays_num) (profit)
```

```
teffects nnmatch (Star2 synthse1 size age year industry pays_num) (profit)
```

```
teffects nnmatch (Star3 synthse2 synthse1 size age year industry pays_num) (profit)
```

```
teffects nnmatch (Star4 synthse3 synthse2 synthse1 size age year industry pays_num) (profit)
```

```
teffects nnmatch (Star5 synthse4 synthse3 synthse2 synthse1 size age year industry pays_num)  
(profit)
```

```
teffects nnmatch (Star6 synthse5 synthse4 synthse3 synthse2 synthse1 size age year industry  
pays_num) (profit)
```

```
teffects nnmatch (Star7 synthse6 synthse5 synthse4 synthse3 synthse2 synthse1 size age year  
industry pays_num) (profit)
```